

MINDFUL EATING BEHAVIORS, BODY IMAGE DISSATISFACTION, AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF WOMEN SUFFERING FROM POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY

Mariam Ejaz^{*1}, Dr Beenish Mubeen², Sumaira Ayub³

^{*1,2,3}Department of Applied Psychology, University of the Management and Technology, Lahore

¹Mariam.sherazi63553@bh.edu.pk, ²beenish.mubeen@umt.edu.pk, ³Sumaira.ayub@umt.edu.pk

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Corresponding Author: *
Mariam Ejaz

Abstract

Background: Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) stands as the predominant endocrine disorder among females, impacting approximately 4-18% of women in their reproductive years. Notably, the prevalence of PCOS among Pakistani women significantly surpasses that of their Western counterparts, reaching 52%, in contrast to the 20-25% prevalence observed among women in the UK.

Objective: The objective of the current study was to find out the relationship between mindful eating behaviors, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life among women suffering from PCOS.

Methods: Cross-sectional research was conducted from October 2022 to August 2023 at the University of Management and Technology. Sample of women suffering from PCOS age ranged 18 to 40 years were recruited from different institutes, hospitals, and clinics, whereas online data was also collected through social media. The mindful eating behavior scale ($\alpha = .89$), Body image dissatisfaction scale ($\alpha = .88$), and Polycystic ovary syndrome quality of life scale (PCOSQOL) ($\alpha = .95$) were used for assessment.

Results: Out of 300 participants 150 (50%) were married and 150 (50%) were unmarried. The overall mean age of the sample was 29.16 years. Results revealed that mindful eating behaviors were found to be positively related to body image dissatisfaction ($p < 0.01$), and body image dissatisfaction negatively related to quality of life ($p < 0.01$). Furthermore, body image dissatisfaction significantly predicted the quality of life ($p < 0.01$). Inter-group comparison of the marital status highlighted significant differences in married and unmarried women in terms of study variables ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion: The study found that mindful eating behaviors are associated with body image dissatisfaction, which is related to poor quality of life in women with PCOS. Significant differences were observed between married and unmarried women regarding these variables. These results suggested that interventions focusing on body image and mindful eating may help improve the quality of life for women with PCOS.

Introduction

Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is one of the most common endocrine disorders affecting women of reproductive age, with global prevalence estimates ranging between 8-13%, and a high percentage of undiagnosed cases, particularly in developing regions ^[1]. PCOS is characterized by hormonal imbalances that affect reproductive, metabolic, and psychological health, leading to compromised well-being and diminished quality of life ^[2]. The condition is the leading cause of anovulation and is responsible for a significant portion of female infertility cases ^[1]. Moreover, PCOS is associated with long-term health risks such as obesity, insulin resistance, and metabolic syndrome, which have widespread effects on both physical and mental health ^[3].

Weight gain and obesity are common among women with PCOS, largely due to insulin resistance and hormonal dysregulation ^[2]. Research suggests that women with PCOS are more likely to engage in disordered eating behaviors, including binge eating, particularly triggered by cravings for carbohydrate-rich and sugary foods. These behaviors are exacerbated by the cyclical hormonal fluctuations related to the menstrual cycle, which intensify cravings and make weight management even more difficult ^[4]. Studies report that obesity and disordered eating behaviors in PCOS significantly increase the risk of metabolic complications, which further exacerbate health issues like cardiovascular disease and diabetes ^[5].

Body image dissatisfaction is highly prevalent in women with PCOS, often driven by the physical manifestations of the syndrome, such as weight gain, acne, and hirsutism ^[6]. Negative body image significantly affects self-esteem and can lead to psychological issues, including depression, anxiety, and social isolation. Social comparisons and societal beauty standards, amplified by social media, contribute to the worsening of body image concerns in this population ^[7]. Studies indicate that women with PCOS often report higher levels of body dissatisfaction compared to those without the syndrome, and this dissatisfaction is closely linked to psychological distress and poorer quality of life. Depression and anxiety are prevalent in this

population, further diminishing their overall well-being ^[8].

Mindful eating has emerged as a potential intervention for improving eating behaviors in women with PCOS. This practice, which involves being fully present during meals and paying attention to hunger and satiety cues, has been associated with better control over binge eating episodes and reduced emotional eating ^[9]. However, studies have shown the benefits of mindful eating in addressing disordered eating patterns, the relationship between mindful eating, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life among women with PCOS has not been thoroughly examined. There is growing evidence that mindful eating may help improve psychological well-being by fostering a healthier relationship with food, but its impact on overall quality of life requires further exploration ^[10]. Despite the substantial research on the physiological and psychological impacts of PCOS, the relationship between mindful eating behaviors, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life remains underexplored. Most previous studies have focused on either metabolic outcomes or psychological well-being in isolation, without investigating how these factors interact in women with PCOS. This study aims to address this gap by exploring how mindful eating behaviors influence body image dissatisfaction and quality of life in women suffering from PCOS. Furthermore, this study will examine differences in these variables between married and unmarried women, as marital status may play a significant role in shaping body image perceptions and eating behaviors ^[11]. So, the following hypotheses were formulated:

There exists a positive correlation between mindful eating behaviors and quality of life, while a negative correlation is observed between body image dissatisfaction and quality of life among women affected by PCOS.

Mindful eating behaviors and body image dissatisfaction are significant predictors of quality of life among women with PCOS.

Differences in mindful eating behaviors, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life are expected between married and unmarried women living with PCOS.

Material and Methods

Cross sectional research was conducted at the Department of Applied Psychology, University of Management and Technology, Lahore, spanning from October 2022 to August 2023. Data collected utilizing a consecutive sampling technique, targeting females diagnosed with PCOS. The participants were recruited from different institutes, hospitals, and clinics where females visited for the treatment of the PCOS including holy family hospital, ikram hospital, Govt trauma center, DHQ hospital, city medical complex etc. The inclusion criteria of the study participants were: 1) females aged 18-40 years with at least matriculation qualification, and 2) diagnosed females who were suffering from PCOS for at least the last 6 months. The exclusion criteria of the study participants were: 1) Those females having any form of physical disability, 2) any diagnosed psychological issues, and 3) were widowed and divorced. Sample size of 300 women (n=150 married, n=150 unmarried) within an age range of 18 to 40 years (M=29.16, SD=±5.00). This sample size was calculated using G-Power software. G-Power required information on the parameters related to power, effect size, and significance level to calculate the minimum required sample size.

*The Mindful Eating Behavior Scale*¹² was used to assess the deviant eating behaviors within the study sample. This scale comprised 20 items rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Never, 2 = Seldom, 3 = Sometimes, 4 = Often, 5 = Very often). Higher scores on the scale denoted greater levels of mindful eating behavior. The scale demonstrated a favorable alpha coefficient of .89, indicating good internal consistency.

*Body Image Dissatisfaction Scale*¹³ was used to assess body image dissatisfaction. This scale consists of 26 items rated on a 5-point scale (0 = not at all, 1 = rarely, 2 = sometimes, 3 = often, 4 = always). It comprises three subscales: Body shape and weight, skeletal features, and facial features. Higher scores indicate a higher level of body image dissatisfaction. The scale demonstrated a Cronbach's alpha value of 0.89, which falls in good range.

*The Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Quality of Life Scale (PCOSQOL)*¹⁴ was used to evaluate the quality of life among participants. This scale comprises 35 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale. Higher scores on the scale indicate a better quality of life, while lower scores signify a diminished quality of life. The scale demonstrated a high level of internal consistency, with a Cronbach's alpha value of .95, which shows very good internal reliability.

All the ethical guidelines were followed while conducting the study. Before participation, written consent was obtained from all participants, following a detailed explanation of the study's objectives and procedures. Participants were informed about their ethical rights e.g., volunteer participation, confidentiality of the information, and right to withdraw at any time of research.

Data were analyzed using SPSS Version 26. Preliminary analysis was done to deal with the missing data and outliers. Before conducting the main analysis, assumptions including normal distribution was also checked. Data of 315 participants was taken out of which data of 300 participants was retained after preliminary analysis. Pearson product-moment correlation was run to see the relationships among study variables. Multiple Hierarchical Regression analyses were run to see the prediction. Furthermore, an independent sample t-test was conducted to assess differences between groups. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

The descriptive statistics of demographic variables is presented in table 1. The participants had an average age of 28.79 years (SD = 2.41). Most were undergraduates (21%), from nuclear families (47%), and equally distributed between married and unmarried (50% each). A majority (71%) had no children. Regarding occupation, 61.5% were working, 24% were students, and 14.5% were housewives. Most belonged to middle SES (82%). Over half (57.5%) had been diagnosed with PCOS for more than a year.

Variables	f (%)	M(SD)
Age	-	28.79 (2.41)
Qualification	-	-
Undergraduate	82(21)	-
Graduate	124(47)	-
Postgraduate	94(32)	-
Family System	221(56)	-
Nuclear	89(44)	-
Joint	-	-
Marital status	-	-
Married	150(50)	-
Unmarried	150(50)	-
No of Children	-	-
None	214(71)	-
1-2	80(27)	-
3-4	6 (2)	-
Occupation	-	-
Working	213 (61.5)	-
Housewife	39(14.5)	-
Student	48(24)	-
Socioeconomic Status	-	-
High	27(13)	-
Middle	254(82)	-
Low	19(5)	-
Duration of Diagnosis of PCOS	-	-
6months	6 (2)	-
9months	22(6)	-
12months	89(34.5)	-
More than a year	183 (57.5)	-

The descriptive statistics and reliability coefficients of the scales are presented in Table2, which indicates that the scales of mindful eating behavior scale showed $\alpha = .79$, PCOS Quality of life with $\alpha = 0.83$, and Body Image Dissatisfaction Scale $\alpha = 0.84$. All the measures of the present study

showed good reliability to carry out further analyses.

Table 2: Psychometric properties and Descriptive statistics of the Scales

Scales	M ± SD	Range	Cronbach's α
Mindful Eating Behavior Scale	71.730±11.750	5-95	0.79
Body Image Dissatisfaction Scale	67.815±15.362	20-113	0.84
Body Shape and Weight	19.62±7.41	2.27-2.57	0.89
Skeletal Structure	29.13±7.39	2.56-2.74	0.76
Facial Features	17.55±5.76	2.21-2.83	0.78
PCOSQOL Scale	120.366±25.316	42-184	0.83

PCOSQOL=The Polycystic Ovary Syndrome Quality of Life

The results in Table 3, revealed significant differences in mindful eating behavior, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life based on marital status among women with PCOS.

Specifically, unmarried women exhibited higher scores in mindful eating behavior, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life compared to married women with PCOS.

Table 3: Comparing marital status in terms of eating behavior, emotional outbursts, and body image dissatisfaction.

Variables	Married (n=150)		Unmarried (n=150)		p-value	Cohen's d
	Mean	±SD	Mean	±SD		
mindful eating behavior	65.56	± 8.92	74.12	± 11.41	***<0.001	0.83
body image dissatisfaction	62.70	±14.91	70.69	± 17.76	**0.001	0.48
quality of life	111.80	± 28.03	124.90	± 22.52	***<0.001	0.61

p <0.01. *p<0.001

Table 4: Correlation of mindful eating behavior, body image dissatisfaction, quality of life

Variables	1	2	3	3	5	6
1. Mindful Eating Behavior	-	0.34**	0.33**	0.25**	0.24**	-0.04
2. Body Image Dissatisfaction	-	-	0.84**	0.82**	0.79**	-0.28**
3. Body Shape and Weight	-	-	-	0.49**	0.54**	-0.19**
4. Skeletal Features	-	-	-	-	0.46**	-0.32**
5. Facial Features	-	-	-	-	-	-0.15**
6. Quality of Life	-	-	-	-	-	-

*p<0.05. **p <0.01. ***p<0.001

The Pearson product-moment correlation analysis presented in Table 4, indicated a significant and positive correlation between mindful eating behavior and body image dissatisfaction, including its subscales: body and weight shape, skeletal features, and facial features, among women with

PCOS. Additionally, the results revealed a negative correlation between body image dissatisfaction and its subscales, and the quality of life among women with PCOS. However, no significant relationship was observed between mindful eating behavior and quality of life.

Table 5: Multiple regression results for quality of life.

Variables	B	95%CI	SE B	β
Constant	138.24	[118.83, 157.64]	9.86	
Mindful Eating Behavior	0.15	[-.13, .43]	0.14	0.06
Body Image Dissatisfaction	-0.47***	[-.66, -.28]	0.09	-0.30***
R ²	0.08			
F (4, 296)	12.85***			

***p<0.001.

The results of multiple regression indicated an 8% variance explained with F (4, 296) = 12.85, p<.001. The results showed that body image

dissatisfaction was negatively predicted (β = -.30, p<.001), while mindful eating behavior did not predict it. (See Table 5)

Discussion

The findings suggested a significant relationship between mindful eating behavior, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life among women with PCOS. The results are consistent with prior research which indicated that females with PCOS have higher body image dissatisfaction, lower self-esteem, and mood swings as compared to the females without PCOS.¹⁵ This seemed to be related to the fact that females suffering from PCOS are at greater risk of body image dissatisfaction due to their disturbed eating behaviors which in turn affect their quality of life. The previous findings also suggested that women experiencing menstrual irregularities due to PCOS tended to exhibit higher levels of body dissatisfaction. Conversely, women with more favorable body mass index ratings demonstrated lower levels of body image satisfaction.¹⁶ PCOS significantly impacts the quality of life of affected individuals. In a multivariate analysis, patients experiencing depression or melancholy exhibited lower quality of life due to the increased symptoms associated with PCOS.¹⁷

The findings also suggested that body image dissatisfaction significantly negatively predicted the quality of life among women with PCOS. These findings may be justified by the fact that women suffering from PCOS exhibited body image dissatisfaction due to BMI and hirsutism rankings and, the presence of acne, this had been related to physical components of quality of life, overall image of one's body, and sexual satisfaction.¹⁸

Indeed, differences exist in terms of body image dissatisfaction, eating behaviors, and quality of life between married and unmarried women diagnosed with PCOS. Concerning menstruation almost more than half of the unmarried females had some form of irregularity. Few of the women had oligomenorrhoea and amenorrhoea. Subsequently, this study found that amenorrhoea, oligomenorrhoea, and severe forms of hirsutism have been discovered within married ladies which later became the premise for locating the genuine incidence of PCOS in our society.¹⁹ Another finding of the study supported the notion that the effects of medication for PCOS, and its

consequences suggested a significant impact of metformin on menstrual irregularities, pimples acne and hirsutism (body image dissatisfaction), mood swings, and each day energy levels of unmarried females more as compared to married females. Findings further proposed that metformin does not produce a significant impact on the capability to conceive and in the change in body weight of the patients, but metformin allows in reducing insulin resistance among PCOS patients which in flip affects power levels and mood swings positively.²⁰

Regarding the Pakistani context, women suffering from PCOS are less aware of this condition whereby neglecting the concept of healthy lifestyles including healthy eating habits which have become the underlying basis for many other emotional and social issues and are all due to extreme hormonal disturbances (sex hormones, hyper androgenism and stress hormones) among women suffering from PCOS.²¹ A study conducted among women with PCOS visiting clinics in three cities of Pakistan revealed that a majority of them exhibited characteristics such as obesity, hirsutism, elevated blood glucose levels, irregular menstrual cycles, and acne. Furthermore, the study reported a prevalent experience of low quality of life and depression among the respondents.²² Women with PCOS often attempt to manage their body image dissatisfaction by exerting control over their eating habits. Clinically, this lack of awareness and unhealthy behavior may result in the development of eating disorders (e.g., binge eating, bulimia nervosa, and anorexia nervosa), which can further aggravate the severity of PCOS. Such complications may lead to more resistant forms of the condition, including insulin-resistant PCOS and adrenal PCOS.^{23, 24} However, the involvement with the social circle, basic awareness related to the signs and symptoms of PCOS, healthy eating, and lifestyles, the importance of mental health and its relation to the effect on body and health, inoculation of exercises can significantly improve the overall psychological and physical health, which not only creates an amazing equilibrium among maintaining these symptoms but also assure the best quality of life of women suffering from PCOS.^{5, 25}

Strengths

The study addresses a significant gap in understanding differences in eating behaviors, body image dissatisfaction and quality of life among married and unmarried females with PCOS in Pakistan, serving as a foundation for future research across psychological, medical, physical, and emotional dimensions. It broadens the perspective on quality of life by integrating eating behaviors, and body image dissatisfaction into the analysis. The research utilized sophisticated statistical techniques to ensure reliable and robust findings.

Limitations

The study was conducted within a limited timeframe, financial constraints, and data collected from only a few hospitals. The sample size included 300 females (150 married and 150 unmarried) aged 18 to 38 years, which does not fully represent the national population. Participants from rural or village backgrounds were excluded due to lack of awareness about PCOS and limited education, leaving a gap in capturing data from this group.

Conclusion

This study underscores the relationship between deviant eating behaviors, body image dissatisfaction, and quality of life among women affected by PCOS. The current study emphasized

better eating habits or healthy lifestyles, including various exercise routines, and consulting mental health practitioners whenever feel the urge or requirement. Hence this will lead to maintaining a better living standard thereby decreasing the causes and symptoms of PCOS and increasing the quality of life to the best.

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Disclaimer: The text is based on an academic thesis. Findings have never been published/presented earlier. The research synopsis obtained approval from the relevant supervisor and Departmental Graduate Committee (DGC), followed by institutional ethical clearance from the Institutional Review Board (Ref. ICPY/20/185).

Consent for Publication: Written consent was taken from the participants.

Availability of the Data: Data set may be acquired upon reasonable request.

Conflict of Interest: None.

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